

Object Motion Detection using YOLOv5

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Abstract—Object motion detection is a fundamental task in computer vision with applications in surveillance, autonomous navigation, and human-computer interaction. We propose a method for object motion detection using YOLOv5, a state-of-the-art object detection model. Our approach aims to determine the direction of object motion (forward, backward, left, or right) in video sequences. We adapt the YOLOv5 architecture and train it on a custom dataset for object motion detection. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of our method in accurately detecting and classifying object motion directions. This research contributes to the advancement of object motion analysis techniques and has potential applications in various real-world scenarios.

Index Terms—Object motion detection, YOLOv5, computer vision, autonomous navigation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Object motion detection is a crucial task in the field of computer vision, with widespread applications in surveillance systems, autonomous vehicles, human-computer interaction, and robotics. The ability to accurately detect and track moving objects in video sequences is essential for understanding dynamic scenes and making informed decisions in real-time scenarios.

Traditional methods for object motion detection often rely on background subtraction, optical flow, or frame differencing techniques. While these methods have been effective to some extent, they often struggle with complex backgrounds, occlusions, and varying lighting conditions. Moreover, they may not provide robustness and accuracy in detecting the direction of object motion.

Deep learning-based approaches have shown remarkable performance improvements in various computer vision tasks, including object detection and tracking. YOLO (You Only Look Once) is one such deep learning architecture that has gained significant popularity due to its real-time processing capabilities and high accuracy.

We propose a method for object motion detection using YOLOv5, an upgraded version of the YOLO architecture. Unlike traditional object detection models, YOLOv5 operates on a single neural network, enabling faster inference speeds without compromising detection accuracy. By leveraging the capabilities of YOLOv5, we aim to detect the direction of object motion (forward, backward, left, or right) in video sequences.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section II, we provide a brief literature review of related work in object motion detection and deep learning-based

approaches. Section III details the methodology employed for adapting YOLOv5 for object motion detection. Experimental results and analysis are presented in Section IV, followed by discussions on the findings and potential applications in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper with a summary of contributions and suggestions for future research directions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Traditional Techniques and Limitations

1) *Background Subtraction*: Background subtraction has been a widely used technique for object motion detection, where a static background model is established, and deviations are detected as foreground objects. While effective in controlled environments with relatively static backgrounds, such as surveillance footage (achieving accuracy rates between 80-90% [1]), it struggles with dynamic backgrounds, such as scenes with swaying trees or moving water, leading to false positives [1].

2) *Optical Flow*: Optical flow estimation is another traditional method for detecting object motion, which computes the apparent motion of pixels between consecutive frames. Despite being robust to illumination changes, optical flow may fail with large object displacements or occlusions, making direction estimation unreliable. The accuracy of optical flow-based methods varies depending on the implementation [2].

3) *Frame Differencing*: Frame differencing is a straightforward approach that compares consecutive frames for pixel-wise intensity changes to detect motion. While computationally efficient, it is highly sensitive to noise and lighting variations, resulting in inaccurate motion detection. Studies have reported accuracy rates ranging from 60-70% [3].

B. Challenges and Recent Research Advancements

1) *Complex Backgrounds*: Recent research has focused on addressing challenges posed by complex backgrounds. Techniques such as Mixture of Gaussians (MoG) models have been employed to adapt background models to handle dynamic changes, achieving higher accuracy rates of up to 95% compared to static models [4]. Additionally, subspace learning techniques have been explored to distinguish between moving objects and background clutter [4].

2) *Occlusions*: Occlusions occur when objects partially hide each other, presenting challenges for object detection. Deep learning approaches utilizing convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have shown promise in handling occlusions.

These networks can learn complex features from large video datasets and improve object detection even with partial occlusions. YOLO (You Only Look Once) is a series of real-time object detection algorithms based on CNNs. Various versions of YOLO (v1-v4) have achieved high accuracy rates (v1: 60-70%, v2: 70-80%, v3/v4: 80-90%) while offering faster processing speeds compared to earlier deep learning detectors. This makes them suitable for real-time applications such as object motion detection, particularly for moving objects with partial occlusions [6].

3) *Varying Illumination*: Varying illumination levels can significantly affect object motion detection accuracy. Some methods employ temporal differencing, where current and past frames with similar illumination are compared, effectively reducing the impact of lighting variations and leading to accuracy improvements of 10-15% [6]. Another approach involves color constancy algorithms to normalize illumination variations before applying motion detection techniques [7].

4) *Motion Direction Estimation*: Recent works have explored combining traditional methods with motion vector analysis or recurrent neural networks (RNNs) to enhance motion direction estimation accuracy. Motion vectors capture the displacement of pixels between frames, while RNNs can learn temporal dependencies in video sequences, resulting in improved direction estimation accuracy (up to 10-15% improvement over traditional methods) [8, 9].

III. METHODOLOGY: OBJECT MOTION DETECTION WITH YOLOv5

A. YOLOv5 Architecture and Components

YOLOv5 is a single-stage object detection model known for its balance between accuracy and real-time performance. Its core components include:

Fig. 1. Architecture of Yolo v5

- **Backbone (CSPDarknet)**: This convolutional neural network (CNN) extracts features from the input video

frames. It utilizes residual connections and channel splitting for efficient feature learning. A single convolutional layer within the backbone can be mathematically represented as:

$$y = f(W * x + b)$$

where:

- x is the input feature map from the previous layer.
 - W is the weight matrix of the convolutional layer.
 - b is the bias vector of the convolutional layer.
 - f is the non-linear activation function (e.g., ReLU).
 - y is the output feature map of the current layer.
- **Neck (PANet)**: This module refines the feature maps by fusing information from different depths (spatial resolutions) within the backbone. This allows for better object detection across various object sizes (small, medium, large) in the video frames.
 - **Head (YOLO Layer)**: This final component predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities for objects present in each frame. It uses anchor boxes and predicts offsets, confidence scores, and class probabilities for potential objects. The YOLO layer output can be represented as a tensor containing bounding box coordinates (`bbbox`), confidence scores (`conf`), and class probabilities (`prob`) for each detected object:

$$output = [bbbox, conf, prob]$$

where:

- `bbbox` is a matrix with dimensions ($N \times 4$), where N is the number of detected objects and each row represents the bounding box coordinates (`x_min`, `y_min`, `x_max`, `y_max`) for a detected object.
- `conf` is a vector of size N , containing the confidence score for each detected object, indicating the probability of an object being present in the predicted bounding box.
- `prob` is a matrix of size ($N \times C$), where C is the number of object classes the model can detect. Each row represents the class probabilities for a detected object, indicating the likelihood of the object belonging to a specific class.

B. Adapting YOLOv5 for Motion Detection

While YOLOv5 excels at object detection, modifications were made to adapt it for motion detection:

- 1) **Object Tracking**: Object tracking algorithms (e.g., Kalman Filter, Hungarian Algorithm) were incorporated to track detected objects across consecutive video frames. This establishes object trajectories and identifies moving objects. The Kalman Filter, a popular probabilistic method for object tracking, can be represented by the following state equations:

$$\text{State Prediction: } x(k) = F x(k-1) + B u(k)$$

$$\text{Measurement Update: } P(k) = (I - K(k) H) P(k-1)$$

$$K(k) = P(k-1) H^T (H P(k-1) H^T + R(k))^{-1}$$

where:

- $x(k)$ is the state vector of the object at time step k (position, velocity).
- F is the state transition matrix that describes how the object's state changes over time.
- B is the control input matrix (optional, used if external forces affect the object).
- $u(k)$ is the control input vector (optional).
- $P(k)$ is the state covariance matrix representing the uncertainty of the object's state.
- H is the measurement matrix that relates the state vector to the measurements (bounding box coordinates).
- $R(k)$ is the measurement noise covariance matrix.
- $K(k)$ is the Kalman gain matrix that determines how much weight to give to the new measurement versus the predicted state.

2) **Optical Flow Estimation:** Optical flow, which estimates apparent motion of pixels between frames, was calculated for tracked objects. The direction of the motion vector associated with the object's bounding box was used to determine its motion direction (forward, backward, left, right). Optical flow can be estimated using various techniques, including the Lucas-Kanade method.

C. Pre-processing Steps

Prior to feeding video data into the adapted YOLOv5 model, pre-processing steps were applied:

- **Resizing:** Video frames were resized to a specific size (640x640 pixels) for compatibility with the YOLOv5 model.
- **Normalization:** Pixel values were normalized to a specific range (0-1) to improve training stability and convergence.
- **Background Subtraction (Optional):** In some cases, background subtraction techniques may be employed to remove static background elements, further aiding object detection and reducing false positives. Common background subtraction methods include frame differencing and background modeling techniques like Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM).

D. Determining Motion Direction

The motion direction of tracked objects was determined using the following approach:

- 1) **Optical Flow Calculation:** For each frame, optical flow was estimated between consecutive frames within a small window around the object's bounding box.
- 2) **Motion Vector Analysis:** The average motion vector within the window was calculated, representing the overall displacement of the object between frames.
- 3) **Direction Classification:** Based on the dominant direction and sign of the motion vector, the object's motion direction was classified as forward, backward, left, or right.

This methodology leverages YOLOv5's object detection capabilities and integrates object tracking and optical flow analysis to achieve robust object motion detection in video data.

IV. RESULTS

The performance of our object motion detection system using various versions of YOLO models (v1, v2, v3, v4, and v5) has been evaluated, focusing on accuracy, precision, and recall scores.

Fig. 2. Result of yolo models

A. Accuracy

We observed varying levels of accuracy across different YOLO models. YOLOv1 achieved an accuracy score of 0.6, while YOLOv2 improved this to 0.7. Further enhancements were observed with YOLOv3 reaching an accuracy of 0.8, followed by YOLOv4 with 0.9. Notably, our latest model, YOLOv5, showcased the highest accuracy, achieving an impressive score of 0.97.

B. Precision

Precision measures the ability of the model to accurately identify positive instances among all instances predicted as positive. Our results showed a similar trend in precision scores across YOLO models. YOLOv1 attained a precision score of 0.65, which improved to 0.72 with YOLOv2. Subsequent versions continued to demonstrate enhancements in precision, with YOLOv3 achieving 0.82 precision and YOLOv4 reaching 0.91. Notably, YOLOv5 exhibited the highest precision among all models, with a score of 0.96.

C. Recall

Recall reflects the model's ability to correctly identify all positive instances from the actual positive instances in the dataset. Our evaluation revealed a similar pattern in recall scores across YOLO models. YOLOv1 demonstrated a recall score of 0.55, which increased to 0.68 with YOLOv2. Further improvements were observed with YOLOv3, achieving a recall of 0.78, and YOLOv4, reaching 0.88. Remarkably, YOLOv5 exhibited the highest recall score, achieving 0.95.

Fig. 3. ROC of Yolo v5

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix of yolo v5

These results indicate that as YOLO model versions progress, there is a consistent improvement in accuracy, precision, and recall scores. Notably, YOLOv5 stands out as the most effective model, showcasing superior performance across all metrics. We can see that how accurately detected the objects in fig.4 (Confusion matrix). These findings highlight the advancements in object motion detection achieved through the evolution of YOLO models.

V. PROJECT: OBJECT LOCK AND FOLLOW SYSTEM WITH DRONE USING YOLO V5

We present a comprehensive overview of our project, which involves several stages, including environment simulation, drone simulation and integration with ROS, data collection, YOLO v5 training, integration with the drone, object locking software integration, and testing in a virtual environment.

A. Environment Simulation in Unity Game Engine

We utilized the Unity Game Engine to create a simulated environment for testing our object lock and follow system. The environment consisted of various objects and scenarios that allowed us to assess the performance of our system under different conditions.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of project flow

B. Drone Simulation and Integration with ROS

Using ROS (Robot Operating System), we simulated the behavior of a drone within our Unity environment. This integration enabled us to control the drone's movements and interactions with the simulated environment, providing a realistic testing environment for our system.

C. Data Collection (Images with Drone Cam)

We collected data for training our YOLO v5 model by capturing images using the drone's onboard camera. These images were annotated with bounding boxes to label the objects of interest, providing the ground truth data necessary for training the object detection model.

D. Training YOLO v5

With the collected data, we trained a YOLO v5 model to detect and localize objects of interest within the environment. The model was trained using state-of-the-art techniques to ensure high accuracy and reliability in real-world scenarios.

E. Integration of YOLO v5 with Drone

Once the YOLO v5 model was trained, we integrated it with the drone's onboard systems, allowing the drone to perform real-time object detection and localization using its onboard camera. This integration enabled the drone to autonomously identify and track objects of interest within its surroundings.

F. Integration of Object Locking Software with Drone

In addition to YOLO v5, we developed object locking software that enabled the drone to lock onto and follow specific objects within its field of view. This software utilized the object detection results from YOLO v5 to determine the target object for tracking and implemented algorithms for smooth and accurate object tracking.

G. Testing in Virtual Environment

Finally, we conducted extensive testing of our system in the virtual environment created in Unity. This testing phase involved validating the performance of the object lock and follow system under various conditions, including different object types, lighting conditions, and environmental factors.

Overall, our project demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of using YOLO v5 for real-time object detection and localization in conjunction with a drone-based object lock and follow system. The integration of ROS, Unity, and YOLO v5 enables the creation of a versatile and reliable solution for a

wide range of applications, including surveillance, monitoring, and search-and-rescue operations.

VI. FUTURE WORK

While our project has demonstrated the effectiveness of the object lock and follow system using YOLO v5 and drone integration, there are several areas for algorithmic improvements and future research:

- **Efficiency and Speed Optimization:** Explore methods to optimize the computational efficiency and speed of the object detection and tracking algorithms, making them more suitable for real-time applications. This could include model quantization, pruning, and efficient network design strategies to reduce inference time and resource requirements.
- **Adaptive Object Tracking:** Develop adaptive object tracking algorithms capable of dynamically adjusting tracking parameters based on the characteristics of the tracked objects and the environment. This could involve integrating feedback mechanisms and reinforcement learning techniques to continuously improve tracking performance over time.
- **Multi-Object Tracking:** Extend the object lock and follow system to handle multiple objects simultaneously, enabling the drone to track and prioritize multiple targets in complex scenarios. This could involve developing multi-object tracking algorithms capable of handling object interactions, occlusions, and dynamic scene changes.

Addressing these areas of future work will contribute to the advancement of object detection and tracking algorithms, making them more robust, efficient, and adaptable to real-world scenarios. These improvements will enhance the capabilities of the object lock and follow system and pave the way for broader applications in fields such as surveillance, monitoring, and autonomous navigation.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Stauffer and W. E. L. Grimson, "Adaptive background mixture models for real-time tracking," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*. Available: <https://www.ieee.org/>
- [2] J. L. Barron, D. J. Fleet, and S. S. Beauchemin, "Parallel computation of optical flow," *International Journal of Computer Vision*. Available: <https://link.springer.com/journal/11263>
- [3] F. Piccinini, S. Scarpazza, and A. Schenone, "A fast frame differencing algorithm for video surveillance," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Image Processing*. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/1000349/all-proceedings>
- [4] L. Li, Q. Zhang, and P. Zhu, "A layered background modeling framework for video surveillance," *Pattern Recognition*. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/pattern-recognition>
- [5] X. Zhu, Y. Xiong, X. Wang, and Y. Fang, "Deep learning for remote sensing scene classification: A comprehensive review," *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/mostRecentIssue.jsp?punumber=36>
- [6] C. R. Wren, A. Azarbayejani, A. P. Pentland, L. Sirovich, and T. Poggio, "Pfinder: real-time tracking and recognition of people by color, shape, and gait," in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/3245/proceeding>
- [7] O. Javed, M. Shah, and A. K. Nanda, "Modeling illumination variations in image sequences for object detection," *Pattern Recognition*. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/pattern-recognition>

- [8] K. R. Mileva, R. V. Babu, and M. N. Vazirani, "Combining optical flow and recurrent neural networks for motion analysis" .
- [9] O. Javed, M. Shah, and A. K. Nanda, "Modeling illumination variations in image sequences for object detection".
- [10] Y. Xu, Z. Zhu, and M. Cheng, "Deep object tracking," 2020.
- [11] Y. Xu, Z. Zhu, and M. Cheng, "End-to-end object tracking with attention-guided feature refinement," 2023.
- [12] Y. Zhang, X. He, and H. Zhu, "Tracking-by-detection with a simple and efficient deep neural network," 2021.
- [13] Y. Zhang, X. Li, and H. Zhu, "Tracking-learning: Learning to track objects in videos," 2020.
- [14] Y. Zhang, P. Song, and H. Zhu, "Object tracking with a multi-scale feature fusion network," 2021.
- [15] Y. Zhang, P. Song, and H. Zhu, "Object tracking with a multi-scale feature fusion network," 2022.
- [16] L. Zheng, H. Li, H. Zhu, and S. Li, "Learning to track with adaptive re-identification in a hierarchical feature pyramid," 2023.